

Design Exploration for an Axisymmetric Rear BLI Propulsor

A. Battiston¹ and R. Ponza²
HIT09 S.r.l., Padova, 35137, Italy

E. Benini³
University of Padova, Padova, 35131, Italy

In the context of aircraft propulsion using Boundary Layer Ingestion (BLI), the possibility to determine a fast and consistent numerical model for the exploration of the design space can lead to a deep insight on the influence of geometrical and functional design variables on the performance of a propulsor. The present work deals with a parametric CFD analysis of a 2D axisymmetric BLI propulsor, aimed at determining the most promising regions of the design space to be considered for further optimization studies.

I. Nomenclature

F	=	gauge force
ϕ	=	wall forces acting on the drag domain
θ	=	wall forces acting on the thrust domain
INT	=	intrinsic net thrust
NAF	=	net assembly force
W	=	power
PSC	=	power saving coefficient
A	=	area
k	=	specific heats ratio
T	=	static temperature
p	=	static pressure
h	=	specific enthalpy
ρ	=	static density
M	=	Mach number
Re	=	Reynolds number
V	=	velocity
C_f	=	force coefficient
τ_{wall}	=	wall shear stress
π_c	=	fan total pressure ratio
η_{pol}	=	fan polytropic efficiency
χ	=	ratio between the shaft power and the net assembly force related power
<i>Uppercases / Lowercases</i>		
O	=	uppercase: total quantity
∞	=	lowercase: freestream conditions
H	=	lowercase: propulsor highlight section
T	=	lowercase: propulsor throat section
I	=	lowercase: propulsor fan intake section

¹ Research Engineer.

² Senior Research Engineer.

³ Full Professor, Department of Industrial Engineering, AIAA Member.

E = lowercase: propulsor fan exhaust section
 N = lowercase: propulsor nozzle exhaust section

Acronyms

BLI = Boundary Layer Ingestion
 CFD = Computational Fluid Dynamics
 $RANS$ = Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes

II. Introduction

Nowadays, aerodynamic optimization of civil aircraft is fundamental in granting the designer novel opportunities to reach increasingly demanding tasks regarding fuel consumption minimization. Higher awareness about the environmental impact of air transportation is in fact leading to more sustainable aircraft technologies, and some of them foresee a closer integration between fuselage and propulsors. Boundary Layer Ingesting (BLI) propulsors are considered one of the most promising solutions when a high level of integration between the engines and the airframe is expected. At a conceptual level, the key for establishing the superiority of a BLI system compared to conventional podded engines consists in the wake filling principle: by ingesting part of the fuselage's low-momentum boundary layer flow, the aircraft wake is re-energized providing a reduction of momentum deficit and, as a consequence, a reduction in the jet velocity necessary to achieve the desired thrust. As a consequence, the equivalent propulsive efficiency is expected to increase in BLI systems.

Currently, different BLI layouts have been proposed [1], such as the propulsive fuselages, rear engines or distributed fans over blended wing body concepts. Configurations such as the blended wing body, although promising, are not expected to be implemented until some decades since they require dramatic changes in the aircraft architecture. On the other hand, the propulsive fuselage concept requires relatively smaller modifications to the classic tube and wing layout and, therefore, could be implemented within a shorter term.

The project named "Support Understanding of Boundary Layer Ingestion Model Experiment" (SUBLIME) is part of the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking Initiative of the European Union, and aims at understanding boundary layer ingestion and demonstrating the capabilities of these new propulsion systems to meet the goals set by ACARE for 2035. SUBLIME relies on both high-fidelity computational fluid dynamics and wind-tunnel testing at transonic regimes to assess the behavior of aircraft architectures suitable for appropriate propulsor installation which minimizes inlet flow distortions and maximizes power saving. In the present work, a parametric study of a rear propulsor unit (hereafter referred to as "BLI-360" configuration) is presented as part of the design activity performed in the SUBLIME project.

III. Scope of the Activity

One of the major challenges in the quantification of a BLI propulsor benefit consists in the definition of proper performance metrics and references. In this regard, the quantification of thrust is not trivial: in fact, the close integration of airframe and propulsor does not allow for a clear distinction between drag and thrust forces [2]. Although such integration provides the possibility for various definitions of thrust and drag, an ambiguity still persists in determining which portion of the airframe contributes to thrust or drag, thus making conventional expressions for the propulsive performance virtually useless.

Therefore, the determination of a consistent thrust-drag bookkeeping scheme is relevant and cannot follow the simple approach used for a classic podded engine. Various bookkeeping approaches have been proposed for the conceptual design phase [3], based on momentum or power conservation [4] approaches. Smith [5] bypassed the problem of non-uniqueness in the definition of installed thrust and introduced a power saving coefficient metric (PSC) that could quantify the benefits in terms of mechanical power needed to propel an aircraft using a BLI engine with reference to a non-BLI configuration when both configurations provide zero net-force balance on an aircraft travelling at a desired Mach number:

$$PSC = \frac{W - W_{BLI}}{W} \Big|_{Flight\ M, NAF=0} \quad (1)$$

Other metrics have been used to determine the benefits of a BLI system: Drela [6] introduced a fuel burn metric to quantify the benefits of a boundary layer ingestion layout for the D8.x configurations. In that case, a 33% fuel consumption reduction has been demonstrated with respect to an optimized conventional transport configuration, with

benefits coming from drag reduction and from the possibility to implement low-sweep wings for reduced structural weight and increased lift coefficient. However, this has been carried out at relatively low Mach number.

At the present state of the art, benefits for BLI propulsors over conventional architectures have not been proved yet for transonic flight conditions. The scope of the SUBLIME project is to contribute to fill this gap, starting from a consistent design exploration of a rear BLI-360 propulsor both in terms of geometrical features (i.e. nacelle shape) and functional variables, such as the fan pressure ratio and the ingested mass flow.

In the present study, a 2D axisymmetric BLI-360 geometry has been considered. Although this choice simplifies the considered model, it is relevant and consistent within the purpose of this work and makes it possible to explore in a relatively short time a significant number of different geometries working at different conditions (i.e. pressure ratio or ingested mass flow).

IV. Parametric Model

A. Geometry and Constraints

The parametric geometry has been defined based on the main geometrical features of a wind tunnel test model of a BLI-360 propulsor that will be eventually tested at transonic flow conditions – $M = 0.8$, $Re \sim 3e6$. Therefore, the choice of the design variables was driven by a number of size and manufacturing constraints. Figure 1 shows an overview of a sample parametric geometry. In addition to a standard tubular fuselage (not shown in Figure 1), the model comprises an aft-fuselage, the nacelle and the tail plug. In the numerical model, two vertical lines are created which represent the fan intake and exhaust sections, where appropriate boundary conditions are applied, as it will be discussed in section IV.B.

Figure 1: Overview of the Parametric Geometry.

Multiple types of curves have been used to generate the final shape. In particular, regarding the intake region internal shape, the curves highlighted in Figure 2 have been selected for a proper geometry representation.

The shroud is composed of an ellipse arc defining the lip, and a 5th order polynomial Bell-Mehta curve from the throat section to the fan-intake section is used. The hub is defined using a parabolic arc, constrained by the fan hub radius and the inclination angles at the highlight section (defined by a design variable) and the fan section (which is zero). In order to maintain a C^1 class of continuity between all curves, the aft-fuselage shape has been generated using a modified Bell-Mehta curve. A classical 5th order Bell-Mehta curve has the following equation:

$$y(t) = y_1 - (y_2 - y_1)[10t^3 - 15t^4 + 6t^5]; \quad t := \frac{x-x_1}{x_2-x_1} \quad (1)$$

As a consequence, the value of the derivative at the final point would be zero. However, by imposing a first derivative value $\dot{y}(x_2) = \dot{y}_2$ and a second derivative $\ddot{y}(x_2) = 0$ at the final point, a more generalized form of the polynomial curve is obtained:

$$y(t) = y_1 - (y_2 - y_1)[(4\delta + 10)t^3 - (7\delta + 15)t^4 + (3\delta + 6)t^5]; \quad \delta := \dot{y}_2 \frac{x_2 - x_1}{y_1 - y_2} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, for a given value of the inclination angle – hence, the derivative –, it was possible to easily obtain a 5th-order polynomial curve that could guarantee the C^1 class of continuity with the hub section parabolic arc while, at the same time, preventing the generation of horizontal inflection points at the highlight section.

As far as the exhaust region is concerned, it is composed of two 5th order Bell-Mehta curves defining the hub and shroud shapes of the nacelle. The tail plug is made up of a circular arc smoothing the connection between the exhaust-hub curve and the final straight line, which features a fixed inclination angle β .

Figure 2: Parametric Geometry, parameters (top) and curves (bottom).

The design variables have been defined in order to provide the parametric model with a consistent degree of freedom: the ratios of highlight, throat, exhaust and fan sections, as well as the inclination angle at the highlight section, the intake axial length and the fan section height were considered as variables for the internal flow. The outer cowl was parametrized in terms of maximum thickness and the relative position $x_{A,rel}$ of the maximum diameter location with respect to the nacelle's length.

The constraints dictated by the wind tunnel test model manufacturing needs consist in the minimum fan hub radius, as well as its axial length, the axial distance from the beginning of the aft-fuselage to the throat section and the imposition of a constant area upstream and downstream the fan region. The exhaust axial length and the tail plug inclination angle were fixed as well. The airframe overall length was about 1.5m.

B. Numerical Model

The CFD study was carried out using ANSYS Fluent®, by creating parametric journal files via Matlab®. The fan model was built by substituting the actual fan with a model using boundary conditions. In order to match the desired values of fan total pressure ratio and polytropic efficiency while assuring the desired mass flow rate it was decided to define such boundary conditions as mass flow outlet (at the fan intake section) and mass flow inlet (at the fan exhaust section).

The mass flow values for both the BCs were not fixed in the CFD pre-processing. Instead, they were defined as named expression. For a compressible one-dimensional flow, the continuity equation can be written as:

$$\dot{m} = A p^0 \sqrt{\frac{k}{R T^0}} M \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M^2 \right)^{\frac{k+1}{2(1-k)}} \quad (3)$$

In the CFD computations, the fan total pressure ratio and polytropic efficiency were imposed:

$$\pi_c = \frac{p_E^0}{p_I^0} ; \quad \eta_{pol} = \frac{k-1}{k} \frac{\ln(p_E^0/p_I^0)}{\ln(T_E^0/T_I^0)} \quad (4)$$

These values were used in the following scheme to assure the desired value of the mass flow within the fan. By writing the continuity equation at the fan exhaust (E) and making the total temperature and total pressure at the fan intake section (I) explicit, it was possible to rearrange equation (3) in the following form:

$$\dot{m} = A_E \pi_c p_I^0 \sqrt{\frac{k}{R T_I^0 \pi_c^{k \eta_{pol}}}} M_E \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_E^2\right)^{\frac{k+1}{2(1-k)}} \quad (5)$$

an expression which could be used to update the mass flow value at the end of a generic CFD iteration: at the j -th iteration, the updated mass flow value to be used for both the BCs at the fan sections was evaluated using the j -th values of Mach number at section (E), total pressure and total temperature at section (I):

$$\dot{m}(j+1) = A_E \pi_c p_I^0(j) \sqrt{\frac{k}{R T_I^0(j) \pi_c^{k \eta_{pol}}}} M_E(j) \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_E^2(j)\right)^{\frac{k+1}{2(1-k)}} \quad (6)$$

Owing to continuity, the same mass flow value resulting from equation (6) was used for both the fan boundary conditions. Also, the exhaust total temperature was updated in a similar way by rearranging the definition of polytropic efficiency:

$$T_E^0(j+1) = T_I^0(j) \pi_c^{\frac{k-1}{k \eta_{pol}}} \quad (7)$$

The strength of this CFD model lies in the following: (a) the fan is modelled only using its design parameters (compression ratio and polytropic efficiency), which makes it possible to study the behavior of a generic propulsor geometry operating at different design conditions without iterating on the mass flow rate in order to achieve the result; (b) although the BCs are treated as mass inlets/outlets, a pre-CFD evaluation of mass flow rate value is not needed, since the its values are updated in the model until convergence. A first guess mass flow rate is still to be made in order to initialize the flow, but this initial value has no impact on convergence. The flowchart of Figure 3 summarizes the necessary steps for getting a converged CFD solution.

Figure 3: Flowchart of Fan Model.

C. Performance Evaluation

In order to assess a global performance metric, a Net Assembly Force (NAF) was defined that takes in account all the forces acting on the airframe. Figure 4 shows the streamwise forces acting on the axisymmetric geometry. The wall forces acting on the drag domain on a generic surface A are denoted by ϕ , whilst the gauge forces at the intake and exhaust sections of the propulsor are denoted by F :

$$\phi = \int_A [(p - p_\infty)\hat{n} + \vec{\tau}_{wall}] \cdot \hat{x} dA \quad (8)$$

$$F = \int_{A,i-A,e} [(p - p_\infty)\hat{n} + \rho\vec{V}(\vec{V} \cdot \hat{n})] \cdot \hat{x} dA \quad (9)$$

Figure 4: Streamwise Forces Acting on the Airframe

The absolute value of propulsor intrinsic net thrust (INT) can be determined as the difference between the gauge forces at the exhaust and intake. As a consequence, the Net Assembly Force (positive when directed along the drag direction) can be defined as the algebraic sum of the Intrinsic Net Thrust and the drag forces acting on the walls in the drag domain:

$$INT = F_N - F_H \quad (10)$$

$$NAF = (\phi_{fus} + \phi_{nac} + \phi_{plg}) - INT \quad (11)$$

A further step was to attribute a NAF value to a reference non-BLI airframe. A reference fuselage drag was provided based on available data on a commercial aircraft, so the ΔNAF metric could be defined as:

$$\Delta NAF = NAF - \phi_{fus,ref} \quad (13)$$

This metric was to be intended as a surrogate of the “net propulsive thrust”, which takes in account the installation effects of the BLI nacelle and the variations in the fuselage shape with reference to a non-BLI configuration. According to this metric, it was possible to introduce a ΔNAF -related power as well, defined as in equation 14. The negative sign was included in order to get a net assembly force positive in the thrust direction.

$$W_{\Delta NAF} = -\Delta NAF \cdot V_\infty \quad (14)$$

In order to quantify the amount of shaft power converted into useful power, the inverse of an efficiency-like figure of merit was defined that takes the a ΔNAF -related power into account in the denominator:

$$\chi := \frac{W_{fan}}{W_{\Delta NAF}} \quad (15)$$

where the shaft power is calculated as:

$$W_{fan} = \dot{m}(h_E^0 - h_T^0) \quad (16)$$

The main strength of above metric relies in the fact that a precise separation of thrust and drag components is not needed, which is actually the main issue when applying a momentum conservation approach in a BLI propulsor analysis.

D. Mesh Topology and Convergence Analysis

The 2D mesh was built based on a semi-structured grid topology. A structured mesh has been used to discretize the region around and within the propulsor and the rear wake, whilst the external flow field has been meshed with an unstructured block. Figure 5 shows an example of the parametric mesh.

Figure 5: Parametric grid topology.

The flow domain extents for $L_x \times L_r = (50 \times 30)L_{fus}$, being L_{fus} the overall fuselage length. The structured wake region extents for $5L_{fus}$. A grid convergence analysis has been carried out, targeting the force values presented in the performance evaluation model. Figure 6 summarizes the mesh convergence study in terms of wall and gauge forces acting on the airframe. The sensitivity analysis led to the choice of a grid with approximately 660k elements, corresponding to the one featuring the lowest values of forces percentage differences with reference to the previous mesh. An average γ^+ value of ~ 0.67 has been achieved.

Figure 6: Grid convergence analysis results.

V. Design Space Investigation

The parametric geometry relied on a set of design variables which are independent from each other, but at the same time, have a strong influence on the curve's shapes. The scope of this design investigation was to assess the impact of some characteristic variables on the performance of a 360 BLI propulsor.

In particular, the first parametric study concerned the analysis on the nacelle's height and intake length, while the second one was focused on the fan hub radius.

A. Parametric Investigation on the Nacelle Height and Length

Regarding the nacelle height, it was decided to freeze a certain nacelle shape and perform the height variations over that nacelle while adapting the exhaust hub curve with the aim of maintaining the same area ratio between the fan and nozzle exhaust sections. As a consequence, these constraints will raise the nozzle hub radius, thus providing different shapes for the exhaust hub curve and plug. The heights variations have been controlled by a variable ΔH defined as:

$$\Delta H := H/H_0 \quad (17)$$

Being H the individual height and H_0 the reference height, correspondent to the lowest value. On the other hand, the variations in the intake length caused a change in the intake region. In order to guarantee the C^1 class of continuity at the connection between curves, slight differences in the shapes had to be taken in account. The variations in the airframe shape concerned only the region from the aft-fuselage to the tail plug.

Figure 7: Variations in the Nacelle Height (top) and Intake Length (bottom).

A set of 10 equally spaced samples for each of the two geometrical features was considered, for a total of 10^2 geometrical individuals. Each individual of the grid population was simulated with 10 different values of the fan pressure ratio, for a total of 10^3 CFDs. Results are shown in terms of shaft to ΔNAF power ratio in Figures 8-9, from which two main conclusions can be drawn: (a) it is apparent that the fan pressure ratio plays an important role in the search for a minimum χ value: the trends show that, for each nacelle length, there is an optimal fan pressure ratio which is located in between $\pi_c = 1.50$ and $\pi_c = 1.60$; (b) the intake length is another significant variable to consider. In fact, increasing the intake length leads to a significant increase in the ratio of shaft and ΔNAF powers. At a first glance, short nacelles seem to be preferable.

Figure 8: Shaft to Δ NAF power ratio as function of the nacelle height.

Figure 9 shows a plot of the parameter χ as a function of the Δ NAF force coefficient, which is defined as:

$$C_{f,\Delta NAF} = \frac{\Delta NAF}{0.5 \rho_{\infty} V_{\infty}^2 c_{mean}^2} \quad (18)$$

With a given value for Δ NAF, the best individual is the one featuring the minimum value of χ , i.e. the individual that could provide the desired Δ NAF with the minimum required shaft power. As consequence, for a set of Δ NAF values, a corresponding set of optimal geometries can be found. It is apparent that the bandwidth that can be observed in Figure 9 represents a qualitative margin for optimization. Since the denominator of χ has a hyperbolic dependence from the abscissa, the ordinate-wise bandwidth represents only the variations in terms of shaft power. It is worth recalling that, for a given Δ NAF, the optimal individual could lie outside the cloud of points due to the fact that this preliminary parametric study did not take into account changes in the nacelle shape.

Figure 9: Shaft to Δ NAF power ratio as function of the Δ NAF force coefficient.

Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the variations in terms of Mach contours and streamlines respectively for an increasing in the nacelle height and an increasing in the intake axial length, for a fixed fan total pressure ratio $\pi_c = 1.45$. Regarding the height variations, it is apparent that an increase in the fan area, while fixing the fan pressure ratio, translates in an increasing in the ingested mass flow. As a consequence, both the shaft power and the intrinsic thrust

are expected to rise. At the same time, a reduction in the ϕ_{nac} contribute on the net assembly force is to be expected when increasing the nacelle height: although higher nacelles provide a greater wetted area, the installation effects will be less pronounced in terms of losses. As seen in the charts of Figure 8, the defined figure of merit χ , which globally takes in account all the contributes, features a minimum within a certain range of fan pressure ratios. This can be seen as the operating range in which the conversion of the fan power into useful power is the most beneficial.

Figure 10: Variations in the nacelle height: Mach Number contours.

Figure 11: Variations in the nacelle intake length: Mach Number contours.

B. Parametric Investigation on the Fan Hub Radius

The previous parametric study on the nacelle length and height was conducted by maintaining the geometrical constraints dictated by the wind tunnel test model manufacturing. However, with the aim of performing a more comprehensive analysis of the design space, it was decided to violate the constraint on the fan hub radius by progressively reducing it from the baseline value to a minimum value correspondent to half the baseline one. This was done in order to assess the effect of an increasing degree of integration of the fan into the fuselage. A set of 11 equally spaced geometries was defined for the parametric study. The nacelle geometry, in terms of both height and length, was fixed to the maximum height value and minimum length value.

Figure 12 shows the trends in the metric χ as a function of the fan hub radius for different values of the fan total pressure ratio. It is apparent that the fan radial position could play a major role in the reduction of χ : in addition, this trend is more prominent for lower FPR values. Also, from the curves' intersections it can be deduced that the optimal values of FPR change while increasing the hub radius. This is also clear when examining the diagram in Figure 13: by fixing a target ΔNAF – hence, its force coefficient – it is apparent that the fan pressure ratio becomes a relevant design variable: the key should be to determine which geometrical shape, working at which FPR, could provide the desired ΔNAF with the minimum shaft power. This is however out of the scope of the current analysis and will be treated in a future work.

Figure 12: Shaft to ΔNAF power ratio as function of the fan hub radius.

Figure 13: Shaft to ΔNAF power ratio as a function of the ΔNAF force coefficient.

Figure 14 shows the effects of the hub radius variations in terms of Mach number contours for a constant fan total pressure ratio $\pi_C = 1.45$. At first glance, a minor hub radius (top figure) features the presence of a small sonic region at the internal lip: by increasing the fan hub radius, this phenomenon tends to mitigate. This is justified by the fact that, having fixed the duct's heights, an reduction in the hub radii corresponds to a reduction in the passage areas. As a consequence, the ratio between the capture and intake areas tends to increase, thus displacing the nacelle stagnation point towards upwards. This translates in an increasing of the intake shroud wall force contribute, which reduces the highlight gauge force. At the same time, a reduction in the contribute of ϕ_{nac} is to be expected, mostly because of the reduction in the external cowl wetted area. This contribute is numerically more important than that of the intake shroud wall. Therefore, a minor loss in terms of shaft to ΔNAF power ratio has to be expected.

Figure 14: Variations in the fan hub radius: Mach Number contours.

VI. Conclusions

In the two parametric studies performed in this paper, the effects of varying some macroscopic geometrical features of the nacelle of a 360 BLI architecture were analyzed based on a tailored performance metric. The first study concerned the nacelle height and the intake length, whilst the second analysis focused on the fan hub radius. The two studies suggest that a geometry featuring short intake and low hub radius would be more promising in terms of enhancements of the parameter χ .

Figure 15 shows a cumulative plot of the fan-to- ΔNAF power ratio versus the ΔNAF force coefficient. The more clustered region at the top side is derived from the first parametric study, whilst the second one produced the point strips at the bottom side.

The cumulative plot shows that the more prominent benefits in terms of required shaft power for a given ΔNAF are achieved by the geometries featuring lower hub radii. Furthermore, from Figure 15, a qualitative map built by drawing best fit curves between all the points at constant FPR was derived which is illustrated in Figure 16. The chart ordinate is the inverse of χ , which defines an efficiency-like metric related to ΔNAF .

Figure 15: Cumulative plot of the Shaft to DNAF power ratio.

It is interesting to note that specific regions of the map correspond to peculiar geometric features of the propulsor: in particular, propulsors with short nacelles and lower hub radii tend to cluster on the top side of the plot, therefore featuring better performance, while nacelles with higher hub radii and longer nacelles are less promising in terms of efficiency. It is apparent that an optimization process should focus on a design space region featuring shorter intakes.

Another conclusion that can be drawn from the chart consists in the qualitative prediction of the BLI propulsor performance referred to the required ΔNAF . Even though the plot was not built based on optimal geometries, it is apparent that larger values of required ΔNAF imply a penalization in terms of χ , since the most promising region is located at low values of ΔNAF .

Figure 16: Qualitative map correlating the geometric characteristics and performance.

Acknowledgments

This study is financed by the Clean Sky 2 project SUBLIME (Supporting Understanding of Boundary Layer Ingestion Model Experiment). The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 864803.

References

- [1] Luca Menegozzo, Ernesto Benini "Boundary Layer Ingestion Propulsion: A Review on Numerical Modeling" *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power*, Dec 2020, Vol. 142, 120801 (15 pages).
doi: 10.1115/1.4048174
- [2] Eric S. Hendricks, "A Review of Boundary Layer Ingestion Modeling Approaches for use in Conceptual Design", *NASA Technical Reports Server*, 2018
- [3] Habermann A.L., Bijewitz J., Seitz A., Hornung M., "Performance bookkeeping for aircraft configurations with fuselage wake-filling propulsion integration" *CEAS Aeronautical Journal*, 11, 2020 pp. 529-551.
doi: 10.1007/s13272-019-00434-w
- [4] Drela M., "Power Balance in Aerodynamic Flows", *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 47, No. 9, 2009, pp. 1761-1771
doi: 10.2514/1.42409
- [5] Smith, L. H., "Wake Ingestion Propulsion Benefit" *J. Propul. Power*, 9(1), 1993 pp. 74-82.
doi: 10.2514/3.11487
- [6] Mark Drela, "Development of the D8 Transport Configuration" *29th AIAA Applied Aerodynamics Conference*, 27-30 June 2011.
doi: 10.2514/6.2011-3970